

THE USE OF ACTION GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL FITNESS IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract

The article discusses the use of outdoor games in the development of physical fitness in schoolchildren

Key words

Physical development, physical perfection, efficiency, modernization, physical qualities

School-age children are characterized by special mobility and a constant need for movement. But when choosing games, the teacher should take into account that the body of younger students is not ready to tolerate long strains. Therefore, the games should not be very long; it is absolutely necessary to stop on vacation.

Mastering skills at this age is more effective at the level of involuntary memorization (in particular, in the game) than arbitrarily. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the anatomical and physiological and psychological characteristics of children of this age. They are highly consistent with various environmental impacts and rapid fatigue.

This is due to the fact that the heart, lungs and vascular system of children of this age are lagging behind in development, and the musculature is still weak, in particular, the muscles of the back and abdominal press. The strength of the supporting apparatus is also still low, and, consequently, the possibility of damage increases (muscle weakness, overstretchedness of ligaments increases the possibility of impaired posture). More suitable games for children of this age are running games, for example, "Wolf in the Moat", in which children have the opportunity to relax after a short run, or games with alternating roles playing in motion, such as "Empty Space".

During this period, it is still difficult for students to isolate individual movements and precisely regulate their individual characteristics. Attention at school age is not stable enough, and therefore outdoor games do not have to require long-term attention from them. The will and inhibitory functions of children are poorly developed, it is difficult for them to listen to the explanation

of the game for a long time and explanations to the end.

It should be borne in mind that schoolchildren of this age can already read and write, which significantly expands their mental horizons, for example, the games "Geese-swans", "Two Frosts", "Owl". In collective games, the simplest ideas about the norms of behavior are put forward. The role and importance of games should occupy a huge place in the life of school age, as it corresponds to their age characteristics. Physical education lessons can consist exclusively of outdoor games. A lesson consisting of games requires organized behavior and some game skills from the student.

In physical education lessons, it is recommended for students to conduct from 3 to 5 games: in the preparatory part - games with low mobility, mainly 2-3 games of great mobility, in the final part - games for the development of attention and low intensity.

Games that improve the balance and coordination abilities of participants are best given in the first half of the main part of the lesson, until attention is weakened by fatigue; game tasks and relay races that develop endurance, after games to improve coordination and speed. Periodically, in the lower grades, you can conduct a competition lesson, i.e. such a lesson, which consists exclusively of outdoor games and various relay races.

In order to effectively conduct outdoor games with younger students, the teacher must take into account the conditions, preparedness and age characteristics of students, as well as the pedagogical tasks of the lesson. Before you start explaining the game, you need to place the participants in such a way that they can see the teacher well and hear his story. It is best to build players in the starting position from which they will start the game.

If the game is played in a circle, then the explanation is in the same circular construction. The teacher takes his place not in the center, but in the row of players. If the players are divided into two teams and are built at a great distance, then for an explanation it is necessary to bring the teams closer, and then let the team move to the start boundaries. In this case, the teacher, explaining the game, stands between the players in the middle of the court, on the side border and turns to one or the other team.

It should be remembered that the presentation of the game must be accompanied by a display. Visibility helps to better understand the game, and after the explanation, the participants will not have any questions. The teacher should stand sideways in a prominent place, or at least face the light, but in order to see all the participants and monitor their behavior.

Explanation of the game. The correct explanation of the game greatly affects

its success. As already mentioned, before starting the game, the teacher must clearly visualize his content, analyze it in advance and only then begin to explain.

The rules should be brief: a lengthy explanation can interfere with the perception of the game. The exception is games in the lower grades, which can be explained in a fabulous, fascinating way. The rule should be logical and consistent. Any game should be explained roughly in accordance with this scheme:

- a) the name of the game (you can tell for what purpose the game is being played);
- b) the roles of the players and their location on the field;
- c) the content of the game;
- d) the purpose of the game;
- e) the rules of the game.

The explanation of the game ends with answers to the players' questions. The answer should be loud, addressing everyone at the same time. Speaking about the course of the game, the teacher will undoubtedly touch on the rules, but at the end of the rules you need to sharpen your attention again so that the children understand them better. The rules should not be spoken monotonously, it is advisable to highlight important points in the game.

The teacher should pay attention to the mood of the students: if they are distracted, it is necessary to shorten the rules of the game. The content of the game is explained in detail only when students play it for the first time. When repeating the game, you just need to recall the main content and explain additional rules and methods.

The teacher in the game must establish such an order in which each child must lead the game (be its captain) in turn. You can assign it in different ways:

- By appointment of the teacher.
- There is a way to choose by lot.
- It is fair to establish a sequence in choosing a commander so that each participant can become one. This contributes to the development of organizational skills and activities.
- You can assign a guide based on the results of previous games.

The player who turns out to be the most agile, fastest, etc., becomes the leading player in the previous game. But it is necessary to inform the participants in advance so that they strive to show the necessary qualities in the games. The negative side of this method is that weak and less dexterous children will not be able to become a captain.

The distribution for teams can also be carried out in various ways:

a) the teacher distributes the players into teams at his discretion in cases where it is necessary to assemble equal teams of forces. This method is most often used in complex outdoor and sports games;

b) another way to distribute players in teams is to build students in a row and calculate for the first or second: the first numbers will be one team, the second - another team. Such a quick distribution is useful for the lesson, since it is limited in time, but its disadvantage is that the teams are not always equal in strength.;

c) you can divide the players into teams using a figure march or calculating a moving column. There should be as many people in each row as are required for the game. This method also does not require much time, but the composition of the teams is random and often unequal in strength;

d) the method of dividing teams by agreement is also used. In this case, the children choose captains divided into pairs (approximately equal in strength), distribute who will be who, and the captains choose them by their names. With this division, the teams are almost always equal in strength. This path is very much loved by children, because this distribution is a game in itself. However, its disadvantage is the inability to use it in lessons: it takes a lot of time;

e) the method of segregation by appointment of captains. Players choose two captains, who, in turn, recruit players to their team.

This is a fairly fast method, and the teams are mostly equal in strength. The negative side of this method is that captains are reluctant to accept weak players, which often leads to insults and quarrels among the players. To avoid unpleasant situations, it is recommended not to make a choice until the end and divide the remaining ones into calculations. The method of appointing captains should only be used in games with high school students who can correctly assess the strength of the players.

For each game, the teacher selects assistants who monitor compliance with the rules, take into account the results of the game and distribute and organize inventory. The number of assistants depends on the complexity of the rules and organization of the game, the number of games and the size of the playing field. The teacher announces the appointment of assistants to everyone who plays. Depending on the complexity of the game and the tasks that need to be solved during the lessons, assistants can explain the rules during the game.

Game management is extremely important. The importance of skillful gameplay management was emphasized by P. F. Lesgaft. "The game must begin in an organized and timely manner, according to a conditional signal (command,

whistle, clapping, waving or coup). Conditional signals are best alternated so that children take into account the accuracy and speed of motor reaction. The teacher warns the children in advance about the signal he has chosen and gives it only after he is convinced that all the players have understood the content of the game and have taken their places. After the game has started, the teacher closely monitors its progress, the behavior of the players, corrects and comments, without catching the general course of the game. If most players make the same mistake, they can pause the game and give instructions on how to perform the tricks of the game correctly, paying attention to tactics. At the same time, he gives children maximum initiative and remains an impartial and objective judge.

If the outdoor game is difficult, the teacher first introduces the children to the basic rules, and then gradually supplements them during the game. To signal the end of the game, it is best when all the participants enjoyed it, but did not overdo it. The game cannot be stopped by shouting, harsh command, as such an unexpected end for students can cause a negative reaction, dissatisfaction. Children often have to restrain themselves while playing. At the limit of its capabilities, a kind of "self-winding mechanism" arises, the basis of which is gaming pleasure. It is important for the teacher to monitor the psychological climate of the mobile game, its process should be pleasant for children.

This is possible only if the participants are active, creative, and independent. It is very important to be able to motivate children in the game. To make the game interesting, it must be in the interests and possibilities of children. It is necessary to pay attention to the desires of the players, their mood. One of the most important tasks of a teacher is the opportunity to join a children's team, to join the field of play activities. Sometimes the teacher can play directly (except for games with competition elements). This is done in cases where you need to show an excellent sample of the ability to play.

By taking part in the game, he not only increases the interest of the players, but also shows them how best to use individual tricks, certain tactical combinations. Negative emotions should not be present in games, it is necessary that games have a positive effect on the nervous system, health and behavior of children. To do this, it is necessary to avoid resentment, anger or fear in games that contribute to the formation of undesirable qualities.

In joint actions, it is necessary to encourage the initiative of each player. It is necessary to teach players not to get lost if they need to switch from attack to defense. But in the case of a transition to protection, players should strive for

"protection - promotion".

To regulate physical and emotional stress, you can use the following methods:

- Change the duration and number of repetitions of game elements.
- Increase or decrease the size of the playing field.
- Complicate or simplify the rules of the game.

An important factor in choosing the dosage of the game is the nature of the previous activity and the mood of the children. If the game is played after a lot of physical or mental effort, it is necessary to suggest a sedentary game that excludes methods that require high stresses. Intense games should alternate with games with low intensities. As the emotional state of the players increases, so does the workload. Children sometimes lose their sense of proportion, striving to surpass each other, do not count on their abilities. They may not feel tired.

Sometimes it is recommended to stop the game, although the players have not yet felt the need to rest. It is desirable that all players receive approximately the same workload. Special attention should be paid to physically weak children. They need an individual dosage: shorter distances, easier tasks, less time in the game. Summarizing the results of the game, determining its results, identifying errors, and wrong actions are of great importance. Before announcing the results of the game, the teacher creates a calm environment, if necessary, collects information from assistants and loudly announces the results. When determining the results of the game, not only the speed is taken into account, but also the quality of the task, which must be warned in advance to the participants. The teacher also evaluates knowledge of the rules and their compliance, the ability to act appropriately and consistently in the game, to use familiar motor actions in certain game situations.

A significant error may be considered improper use of previously acquired motor actions that affect the course of the game or do not meet the requirements of game ethics. In power games, these are excessively sharp pushes that cause falls, in ball games - improper ball retention to the detriment of collective play, as well as ignorance or violation of the basic rules.

Summing up the game has pedagogical value for the teacher himself: observations and conclusions made during the game, which the teacher cannot share with the children, are of great importance for working with the children's team and each student individually.

In addition to a direct assessment of the implementation of the methods

and rules of the game, which were discussed earlier, in the process of conducting various games, the teacher can make the following observations about the behavior of students in order to clarify the characteristics of their physical development, temperament and character:

- to assess the overall physical development of the child;
- the degree of development of individual physical qualities;
- the ability to combine these motor qualities in the game;

When announcing the results, it is necessary to discuss the game together with the participants, identify their mistakes and point out the positive aspects, mark the participants who performed well in individual roles, as well as those who followed the rules of the game and showed creative initiative. In such a discussion, the rules are better understood, the details of the game are indicated, and conflicts are resolved. The analysis helps to understand how well the game is mastered, which players love and what they need to work in the future.

School childhood is a period when the process of further development of individual psychological and formation of basic socio-moral qualities of a person takes place. In elementary school, there is a psychological restructuring in the child's activity, because previously the dominant role of play as a tool of cognition passes to teaching. The game is the most mastered activity by younger students. In it, they take samples to solve new life problems that have arisen in knowledge, in work, in creativity. Therefore, relying on the game is the most important way to include children in educational work without psychological shifts and overloads.

In the pedagogical process, the game performs a number of functions: educational, entertaining, communicative, relaxation, psychotechnical, self-expression, compensatory. The game method is used in the process of sports training not only for initial movement training or selective impact on individual abilities, but also for comprehensive improvement of motor activity in complicated conditions.

Play activity affects the formation of arbitrariness of mental processes, it is in the game that arbitrary attention and arbitrary memory begin to develop, in the game children focus better and remember more. Conscious activity stands out earlier and easier in the game. Following the rules in itself requires the child to focus on the content of the game, its actions and plot. The need for communication and emotional encouragement push the child to purposeful concentration and memorization. Actions in a story-role-playing game create the basis for the development of a special property of thinking that allows you to

transform into a character, anticipate and build your behavior accordingly, contribute to the successful socialization of the child. The game has an impact on personality, because in the game the child not only satisfies his motor activity, but also gets acquainted with behavior and relationships between people, rules of behavior, compliance with which contributes to the formation of volitional regulation of behavior. Playing as one of the leading activities contributes to the development of reflexive thinking, which means the ability to analyze one's own actions, deeds and motives, correlate with the actions, deeds, motives of others and universal values.

In the game, the child acquires communication skills, develops communication skills. The game, its meaning, consists in the development and exercise of all the abilities and inclinations of the child, leading the development and creating a zone of immediate development. The game can serve as a diagnostic tool to determine the level of development of a child, as well as stimulate research behavior aimed at finding and acquiring new information, develops cognitive abilities, observation, intelligence and curiosity.

The game forms abstract thinking, generalization and categorization, due to its abstraction from a specific subject situation. Role-playing games develop arbitrary attention and arbitrary memory through the reproduction of the inner content of the role and the desire for its best performance, which is of great importance for the success of school education.

Separating oneself from others is possible only in a collective role-playing game, which contributes to the perception of not only one's own position, but also the position of other participants. It is noted that the game is the best opportunity to harmoniously combine learning and development.

The game promotes the development of perception of individual things, observation, the formation of generalizations, improvement of coordination abilities, speed, strength, accuracy, endurance. When teaching children, it is now almost universally recognized that there is a need to use game methods in educational activities, but the same task can be successfully solved by applying individual elements of educational activities in the game. At any stage of development, in any form, the game contributes to the intellectual, emotional and moral development of the child.

Competitive games are also of great importance in the development of the psyche, which provide a number of opportunities for personal development, orientation towards the achievements of peers, the desire to be like everyone else, stimulates the development of the child, increases the level of his claims. At

the same time, the possibility of failure is inherent in competitive gaming activities. It is important that the unrealized claims of the child do not deprive him of the desire for success in the future, because very often the child simply refuses to participate in further games.

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